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SONNET – SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, success and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector

D7.4 (D29):

SONNET Energy Reads including infographics

Project Coordinator: Fraunhofer ISI (Karoline Rogge)

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PROJECT PARTNERS

No	Participant name	Short Name	Country code	Partners' logos
1	Fraunhofer Society, with its Fraunhofer Institute of Systems and Innovation Research (Fraunhofer ISI)	ISI	DE	Fraunhofer ISI
2	Dutch Research Institute for Transitions	DRIFT	NL	
3	University of Sussex, with its Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU)	UoS	UK	
4	Grenoble Ecole de Management	GEM	FR	
5	Akademia Leona Kozminkiego	ALK	PL	
6	Zuercher Hochschule for Applied Research	ZHAW	CH	
7	ICLEI European Secretariat	ICLEI	DE	
8	City of Mannheim	MANN	GER	
9	City of Antwerp	ANTW	BE	
10	City of Bristol	BRIS	UK	
11	City of Grenoble	GREN	FR	
12	City of Warsaw	WARS	PL	
13	City of Basel (Associated Partner)	BASE	CH	

Executive Summary

D7.4 compiles the five Energy Reads and five Infographics produced throughout the SONNET project. These outputs sought to translate select (exploitable) SONNET research outputs into succinct, visual and readable formats, in order to increase SONNET's reach and impact.

The first Energy Read & Infographic set the scene for SONNET's work by defining key terms and introducing the SONNET Typology of social innovations in energy (SIEs), on which future SONNET research builds. The second Energy Read & Infographic synthesise key findings from the SONNET Case Studies, with introductions, insights, and recommendations for each of six SIE fields explored in the case studies. Third, findings from the six SONNET City Labs were compiled alongside recommendations for other cities interested in making use of the City Lab method. Fourth, an Energy Read & Infographic define and make use of the concept of 'institutional work' to outline how SIEs can impact (and are impacting) energy systems. Lastly, the fifth and final Energy Read & Infographic bridges the local and European levels, shedding light on how local SIEs can help achieve European energy goals, and how EU institutions can better harness the transformative potential of SIEs.

The Energy Reads build on one another, going from general to specific, and then zooming out again to draw larger-picture reflections. The first 'sets the scene', describing the diversity of SIEs. The second goes a bit deeper, examining certain SIE fields in certain countries. The third refines information further by examining six practical SIE experiments. The fourth then begins to zoom-out again, looking at how social innovations change energy systems. And the final Energy Read zooms-out further still, to link local and European work.

Finally, this deliverable also presents the two SONNET videos that served to "bookend" our work.

All SONNET Energy Reads and Infographics are available to download on our website at: <https://sonnet-energy.eu/project-outputs>. The SONNET videos are part of our YouTube playlist: <https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PLv-mhCFisOsWm6lmbjHCu4ohbM6B2gBXu>.

1 SOCIAL INNOVATION MEETS ENERGY

This first [Energy Read](#) and accompanying [Infographic](#) introduce the concept of social innovation in energy transitions

The SONNET project has worked to understand and show the diversity of social innovation in energy transitions; diversity that goes far beyond 'only energy cooperatives'. This includes presenting a typology of social innovations in energy (SIEs), constructed based on identification and analysis of 500 SIEs from eight European countries. This typology furthermore defines two dimensions with which SIEs are grouped: social relations (cooperation, exchange, competition, conflict) and the types of energy activities (doing, thinking, organising).

By supporting improved understanding of the diversity of SIEs and two key distinguishing SIE dimensions, practitioners, policy-makers and researchers can better understand how to support and harness the transformative potential of such innovations.

Click on the images below to open the full [Energy Read 1](#) and [Infographic 1](#).

Energy Read

Infographic

2 SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ACTION

The SONNET team reviewed 298 documents, conducted 171 in-depth interviews, and took on participant observation in 37 events, all in order to create 18 in-depth case studies and 6 country reports. This second Energy Read pulls out the highlights and most important information from this vast compendium of work.

SONNET researchers identified six varied and important “SIE-fields”, and prepared three case studies per field, each of which examined that field in a different country context.

The [second Energy Read](#) brings this knowledge together. It goes through each of the SIE-fields, providing an introduction to each field, key insights, recommendations, and quotations from those interviewed as part of the case study research.

Compiling the case studies was a large and iterative undertaking. To improve transparency and potential replicability, the Energy Read ends with an [infographic](#) that outlines the research process followed to put together the case studies, including insights from researchers who took on this work.

[Click on the images below to open the full Energy Read 2 and Infographic 2.](#)

Energy Read

Infographic

3 SOCIAL INNOVATION IN PRACTICE

A hallmark of the SONNET project has been partners' work preparing, implementing and analysing the "City Lab" method, as an innovative way to advance local energy transitions.

The [third Energy Read](#) makes use of visuals and key messages to share what each of the six SONNET cities accomplished and learned from their City Lab, and what specific actions they implemented using this method. It closes with a series of recommendations – based on cities' experiences and research conducted to compile a practical "City Lab Guide" – for cities who want to make use of this method too.

The Energy Read is complemented by a series of [infographics](#), which visually depict each SONNET cities' actions and research partners.

Click on the images below to open the full Energy Read 3 and Infographic 3.

Energy Read

Infographic

4 SOCIAL INNOVATION AS TRANSFORMATIVE

SONNET sought to better understand how social innovation changes energy systems. This led to the use of concepts like “institutionalism” and “institutional work”, which shed light on how SIEs play a role in creating, transforming and maintaining institutions that are part of our energy systems – and thus how they can drive energy transitions.

This is a complex topic. As such, the [fourth infographic](#) visually depicts what we mean by “institutions”, “institutional work”, and “institutionalisation processes”.

The [fourth SONNET Energy Read](#) makes use of these concepts to map out how, in practice, six SIE-fields (the same six that were the focus of the SONNET Case Studies) transform and impact energy institutions. For each field, the Energy Read defines: the key actor in the field (e.g. local administrations); how the SIE-field changes social relations; how it creates, maintains or transforms energy regulations, norms and/or cultures; and how it contributes to sustainable energy systems.

The Energy Read closes with reflections for local governments, including reflections specific to each SIE-field, as well as overarching ones.

[Click on the images below to open the full Energy Read 4 and Infographic 4.](#)

Energy Read

Infographic

5 SOCIAL INNOVATION IN EUROPE

The [fifth and final SONNET Energy Read](#) connects local and European initiatives.

First, it outlines what SONNET research – in the form of surveys, interviews and a workshop – has unearthed regarding the degree to which on-the-ground SIE-initiatives can (and do) help meet European Energy goals.

Second, it outlines findings regarding how the EU can, in turn, help on-the-ground SIE-initiatives, in order to better harness their full potential.

The accompanying [infographic](#) distils the key points into one graphic that creates a bridge between SIE initiatives on-the-ground, and EU policy-makers.

Click on the images below to open the full Energy Read 5 and Infographic 5.

Energy Read

Infographic

6 GETTING VISUAL: SONNET'S VIDEOS

The SONNET project was “bookended” with two videos: one to introduce the project and concepts, and a second to summarise and amplify results.

The [first video](#) has hundreds of views and has been featured in a variety of SONNET events. It introduces our objectives, why it is important to look at social innovation in energy, and presents the project’s first research output: a typology of the diversity of SIEs based on analysis of 500 European initiatives.

This first video was created at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic. Not being able to film footage live inspired SONNET to pivot, and to create a collage-style video that combines animation with short, filmed interviews with Project Coordinator (Karoline Rogge), an academic partner (Julia Wittmayer), and a city partner (Jana Deforche).

Click on the image below to watch the first SONNET video.

The second SONNET video has been scripted, animated and prepared, with a slot reserved to include footage captured during the final SONNET event on 28-29 April.

The [SONNET final conference](#) was a key moment for the project, which amplified its results, found synergies with three sister projects (who co-organised the event), and launched an impactful [Joint Policy Brief](#), co-authored with the same three sister projects. It was thus considered to be crucial that the final event be captured and reflected in the final SONNET video. This is why the video will not be published until May 2022 – after the final conference.

The video includes an overview of the SONNET results, sorted into six categories: “the concepts”, “the politics”, “the experiences”, “the locals”, “the process” and “the evaluation”. It features footage from an in-person SONNET on Tour event in Bristol (UK), a short interview with Karoline Rogge,

and footage from the final SONNET conference. It will be published to the SONNET YouTube playlist and on the SONNET website in May.

Figure 1: A preview of the full storyboard for the second SONNET video

7 APPENDIX 1: EC SUMMARY REQUIREMENTS

Changes with respect to the DoA

The DoA specified that both SONNET videos would be included in D7.4. However, SONNET deemed it crucial to include footage from the final SONNET conference – on 28-29 April – in the second video. This report thereby compiles all five Energy Reads, five infographics, the first SONNET video, and a preview of the second video, which is finalised other than the insertion of footage from the final conference.

Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable compiles a number of dissemination, uptake and exploitation outputs, all of which are available on the SONNET website. This deliverable will also be made publicly available as soon as it is submitted.

Short Summary of results

This report compiles twelve outputs, each of which translate extensive and complex scientific results into succinct, visual, and readable publications.

These outputs – encompassing five Energy Reads, five infographics and two videos – build on one another, first building-up increasingly in-depth analyses, and then zooming out to draw more overarching reflections on how social innovations can (and do) transform energy systems, and how their full potential can be better harnessed.

Evidence of accomplishment

This deliverable.

